

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Project Video

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarizes the steps taken to conceive, design, and produce the Ecobulk Promotional Videos. Two videos were planned, with one at the beginning to introduce the project and one towards the end to promote the results.

The goal for the first video is to have a short introduction to the project, with just enough detail to interest viewers in finding out more about the project. The role of the video is twofold:

1. Serve as a standard introduction for the project, that can be used at events for promotional purposes.
2. Serve as a social media content video that can be used to promote the video online.

With these two roles in mind, the video had to appeal to both lay people and more advanced technical viewers. This meant trying to include enough detail to pique the interest of people that already have a good idea of Circular Economy topics, while at the same time also introducing the topic in a way that is understandable for those that are encountering Circular Economy for the first time.

An analysis of the messages and key points was developed into an initial proposal for the structure of the video. This was then refined through an iterative feedback process and translated into the necessary visuals, storyboard and eventually the narrative script for the voice-over.

The final version of the first video is available on the project website: <https://www.ecobulk.eu> and on Youtube: <https://youtu.be/iOLER8eYZ8Y>

The goal for the second video was to have a short overview of the results of the project, with just enough detail to interest viewers in finding out more about the results of the project. The role of the video is twofold:

1. Summarize the project results.
2. Serve as a social media content that can be used to attract people to find out about the project.

Much like the first video it had to appeal to both lay people and more advanced technical viewers. The one thing that both audiences agree on is the interest in the more concrete results of the demonstrators. For this reason it was chosen to focus on the prototypes more than anything else.

An overview of the prototypes and their key results was developed into an initial proposal for the structure of the video. This was then refined through an iterative feedback process and translated into the necessary visuals, storyboard and eventually the narrative script for the voice-over.

The final version of the second video is available on the project website: <https://www.ecobulk.eu> and on Youtube: <https://youtu.be/MrLr3yhbhOI>

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Description of the document and purpose

The ECOBULK promotional video is the first of two videos planned for the WP9 communications package. This video will be used to introduce the main reasoning and purpose behind the project, as well as the demonstrations that are planned. A second video was produced when it was time to share the results of the project.

The first video is available on the website, www.ecobulk.eu as well as on the [Ecobulk Promo Videos YouTube Channel](#), on the link <https://youtu.be/iOLER8eYZ8Y>

The second video is available on the website, www.ecobulk.eu as well as on the [Ecobulk Promo Videos YouTube Channel](#), on the link <https://youtu.be/MrLr3yhbhOI>

The videos have been developed by ISWA with the collaboration of the consortium. This document presents a description of the video production process.

1.2 WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

The videos are part of the task 9.2 Digital Communications, but indirectly a result of all the previous work done for the baseline product selection, circular design framework, and re-design workshops and tools, as well as the development of the prototypes and implementation of the demonstrators.

2 VIDEO 1 DESCRIPTION

This chapter will give an overview of the first video from a functional and design perspective.

2.1 Overview

Main Message:

The message is the announcement of a circular design framework and its role in a demonstration project of a design-led circular approach to bulky composite products in the automotive, construction and furniture sectors.

There should also be a clear message that the circular approach should be about value retention, and that recycling is a last resort in this context.

Target Audiences:

- Circular Economy Stakeholders – the project goals are mostly relevant to people who might want to engage in similar projects, our aim is to convince stakeholders rather than to move general opinion.
- Public – while not directly targeting the public in general, the video should communicate the essence of the project and necessity for it in a way that is also understandable for non-experts who are already interested in Circular Economy topics, so that we can promote the concepts of design led circularity and the focus on value retention.

Message Level: Technical

The project and the topic are too complex and nuanced to be able to present the message at a level for all audiences, within a reasonable video length. We have to assume some general knowledge of circular economy and at least a recognition of composite materials as a type of plastic materials.

Stakeholders without this knowledge are probably not in the right context to implement or champion this in their own context.

People from the public without this knowledge are probably also not interested in Circular Economy, and it is beyond the scope of both the project and this video to either interest them or educate them fully in the subject.

2.2 Narrative Structure

Circular Economy

The circular economy strives to make products last longer, have more re-use options, and make it easier to maintain and recover the inherent value of the constituent parts and materials. The ultimate goal is to get to a closed loop system, one in which all inputs to a product can eventually be reused, replaced, refurbished or recycled into new ones.

Products designed never to become waste.

Composite Challenge

There are many projects developing circular models, but generally with easy to recycle materials. Ecobulk is one of the only ones dealing with a class of materials mostly considered unrecyclable – thermosetting plastic composites FRPs. Composites are generally landfilled or incinerated which is very wasteful considering the high value and inherent energy in these materials.

Composites are also very useful popular materials, with production growing at a fantastic rate (growth stats). They are light, but very strong, and stable, making them very good for saving energy (auto example, reduce in weight = reduce in consumption). Ecobulk will be tackling circular approaches to composites in the automotive, construction and furniture industries.

Design Led

Ecobulk plans to introduce an end-to-end solution to help make complex, bulky composite products and materials more circular. While there are many components which are of equal importance to the resulting circular cycle, this project emphasizes the necessity of products to be designed with circularity in mind – we could say that the project is design led.

The design of the product involves bringing many parts of the chain together, including the supply chain through the choice of materials, the form and function of the product through the business case, and specifically for Ecobulk its end-of-life options. It is the project's argument that the design phase, a moment where all these factors must be brought together to create a coherent product, is a crucial and perhaps most significant place to start the circular process design. Decisions made at this stage will either enhance or cripple the product's ability to enter a circular value chain.

Design Framework

To guide the design stage into making more circular compatible choices, the partners have developed a Circular Design Framework. This framework helps product designers to consider the relevant options available to promote circularity and promote brainstorming and ideation to develop new possibilities in relation to the specific product, material, process, logistics and value chain being considered.

Demonstrations

The design framework is being used to design new more circular parts and products to replace existing linear ones in the automotive, furniture and construction sectors.

1. Central console parts in cars – designed to be modular for re-use and replacement, with materials that can be recycled.
2. Light construction and utility/storage units – designed to be built in modular designs, using materials recycled from other end-of-life composite applications such as wind turbines.
3. Furniture and parts – designed to be modular and easy to refurbish, built from natural and recycled materials.

Call to Action

Get in contact with or follow the project to learn more about framework and the wider circular model being developed by Ecobulk.

3 VIDEO DESIGN

The video was designed in an iterative process and in full consultation with the project partners. An initial script proposal was circulated, and feedback was gathered among the partners. This was done several times to refine the important messages and information, as well as to ensure that the information was correct. This was then translated into visuals, and finally a narrative script was written for the on-screen narration of the video.

3.1 Initial Script Proposal

Video length: 2 minutes

The initial script was developed based on the choice for a video length of approximately 2 minutes. Given the target audiences and purpose of the video, as well as the likely channels being either presentations or social media, it is important to keep the video short and succinct.

Text = Voice over,

[Text] = info for possible visual cues

<... Introduction...>

Thermosetting composite products and materials (known as FRPs) are a tough challenge for the circular economy as they cannot be re-processed and formed again by applying heat.

<... The advantages of composites...>

Composites can be lighter, stronger and more resistant than traditional materials, enabling more sustainable solutions. In cars, 10% less weight can result in 6%-8% less fuel consumption.

[A 10% reduction in weight for cars can lead to a 6-8% reduction in fuel consumption.]

<... The problem with composites...>

But FRP-composite products have until today been practically impossible to reuse or recycle; and by 2023, production will reach 108 billion dollars annually. With a 60% landfill rate, that is a huge loss in value.

[Growth of composite material market 4.1% annually, reaching 38 billion dollars in 2023. Global composite product market expected to reach 108 billion dollars by 2023.]

[Europe produces 50 million tonnes bulky waste, only 40% recycled. Of the 60% wasted (mostly landfilled), 70% are minerals, wood and plastics]

<... Why circularity with composites...>

[Thermoplastic composites, like PE and PP reinforced with fibres and other non-polymeric materials, are different from FRPs and can be processed again into a new product with common industry methods like extrusion by heating and melting the recycled plastic. Thus there is a good reason to favour recycled and even waste thermoplastic and reinforce those with fibrous materials available at low cost from various sources like construction and demolition wood waste (known as wood-plastic composites WPCs) but equally also recycled FRP from wind turbines. By using a thermoplastic polymer matrix these re-manufactured products not only open a way for recycling FRPs but also maintain their circularity to be used again!]

Increasing circularity helps – for example reusing textiles retains 9,6% of the value versus 0.4% with recycling.

[Reusing a ton of textiles retains 9.6% of the original value compared to recycling (0.4%), while car reuse retains 5.3% of the original value against its recycled parts (1.5%).]

<... What is ECOBULK ...>

ECOBULK is a large-scale demonstration of a design led circular approach and business model for composite materials and products. New solutions will target each stage in the product lifecycle.

[Ecobulk product lifecycle stages diagram]

<... Framework Overview ...>

ECOBULK has created a new Circular Design Framework, to help designers and manufacturers consider how products can be used, repaired and refurbished to maintain higher value for a longer time. Material and energy recovery through recycling is a last resort.

[Ecobulk Design Framework Diagram]

[Ecobulk Design Framework sample – Wind turbine challenge]

<... Demonstrations ...>

Demonstrations include the automotive, construction and furniture sectors – but the results are applicable to any industry.

The new motorsport park Kymiring under construction in Finland will use various ECOBULK solutions for lightweight construction applications using new circular composite materials from recycled multilayer pipes and composite turbine blades.

[One application among half a dozen is a modular shelter for visitors in case of rain. The shelter length can be extended to hundred meters long by connecting 3x3m size modules to each other. It is designed from just two ECOBULK products made by Conenor; a plank and panel. Connections made with bolts are quick and easy to remove for disassembly as well as re-assembly in another location. The long lasting new composite parts can be machined like wood for reuse and

finally returned back to composite manufacturers for recycling and remanufacturing.]

[Kymiring material; shelter module]

In Italy, new furniture designs will feature innovative binding methods and recycled materials that can be reused many times.

[Moretti Compact material]

New modular console parts for cars, made from circular bioplastics, will demonstrate how parts can be easily replaced and refurbished.

[Microcab / MAIER material]

<... Call to action ...>

Follow our progress on the web and social media.

[To find out more, please visit the ECOBULK (www.ecobulk.eu) website, and follow us on Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn]

3.2 Description of Action

For each narrative scene, a corresponding action on screen was then described.

Thermoset composite products and materials, also known as FRP, are a challenge for the circular economy.

A modern-looking car appears on screen (on a forest road). The camera zooms into it, and once inside the car, it shows the front panel (the console). From it, a rectangular piece (of composite material) is detached. The rectangular piece flies towards the camera and we see how its different layers are separated.

Composites can be lighter, stronger and more resistant than traditional materials, enabling more sustainable solutions. In cars, 10% less weight can result in 6%-8% less fuel consumption.

Everything disappears except for the rectangular piece of composite material. Icons depicting the concepts 'lighter', 'stronger', 'resistant' and 'sustainable' are drawn (in sync with the voiceover) around the composite material (conveying the fact that 'lighter' + 'stronger' + 'resistant' = 'sustainable'). The icons then disappear, and the front panel of the car reappears. The rectangular piece of composite gets reattached, and we then zoom out of the car, returning this way to the start of the 1st scene. Finally, the following caption is shown: "10% LESS WEIGHT CAN RESULT IN 6%-8% LESS FUEL CONSUMPTION".

But FRP composite products are difficult to reuse or recycle; and by 2023, production will reach 108 billion dollars annually. With a 60% landfill rate, that is a huge loss in value.

The car remains on screen, but the forest background is progressively replaced by a dirty-looking junkyard. Our car starts getting crushed by a car crusher. The screen then gets divided into two (with a diagonal line). The car keeps on getting crushed on the left side, while on the right we find ourselves at a manufacturing plant, seeing how several conveyor belts carry newly-manufactured composite product parts. After a little while everything becomes blurred (becoming the background), and in the foreground the following caption is shown: "HUGE LOSS IN VALUE".

Increasing circularity helps – reusing textiles retains 9,6% of the value versus 0.4% with recycling.

We zoom into the "O" of the word "LOSS" in the earlier caption. We then make everything around the "O" disappear. An arrow is placed onto the "O" (see the circle in the middle of this picture), and the following caption is shown: "REUSING TEXTILES RETAINS 9,6% OF THE VALUE". Then a recycle icon (see the icon on the right of this picture), slides downwards from under the "O", and next to it the following caption appears: "RECYCLING TEXTILES RETAINS 0.4% OF THE VALUE".

ECOBULK is a large-scale demonstration of a design driven circular approach and business model for composite materials and products, with solutions targeting every stage in the lifecycle.

We transition to a new screen in which the ECOBULK logo is shown. We then replicate (but following the visual style of our video) 0:00 to 0:05 of this ECOBULK animation (without the caption at the top).

ECOBULK is creating a new Circular Design Framework, to help designers and manufacturers consider how products can be used, repaired and refurbished to maintain higher value for longer. Material and energy recovery through recycling is a last resort.

We replicate (but following the visual style of our video) 0:05 to 0:22 of this ECOBULK animation (without the caption at the top), adapting the sequence to make it well aligned with what is being narrated by the voiceover.

Demonstrations include the automotive, construction and furniture sectors – but the results are applicable to any industry.

The icon of the manufacturing plant remains on screen and everything else disappears. We zoom a bit into it. A circle is drawn around it (becoming a central node of a star network). Then three smaller nodes appear from underneath the central node, each with an icon of the mentioned sectors: 'automotive', 'construction' and 'furniture'. Then additional nodes branch out from the central node with symbols of other sectors (aerospace, computers, home appliances, textile and ships).

The new motorsport park Kymiring, under construction in Finland, will use ECOBULK solutions for lightweight constructions using new materials from recycled multilayer plastic pipes and composite turbine blades.

A bird's eye view of the new motorsport park Kymiring is shown. Then different reusable elements within it (see slide 7 of this presentation) are highlighted.

In Italy, new furniture designs will feature innovative binding methods that avoid toxic substances and use recycled materials that can be reused many times.

We transition to a new scene in which a piece of furniture (confirm type of furniture to be shown) appears on screen. The camera zooms into a specific part of it and shows how, instead of using glue to attach together two different parts, it features an innovative binding method (provide details of binding method to be shown).

New modular console parts for cars, made from circular bioplastics – thus avoiding the use of fossil fuels - will show how parts can be easily replaced and refurbished.

We come back to seeing the front panel of the car in the first scene of the video, and we show how a part of its centre console is replaced.

Follow our progress on our website and social media.

We transition to the final scene of the video in which the ECOBULK logo (pending reception in vector format) is shown, and below it:

- The web page of the project:
<https://www.ecobulk.eu/>
- The twitter page (with a twitter icon): <https://twitter.com/EcoBulkEU>
- The facebook page (with a facebook icon):
<https://www.facebook.com/EcoBulkEU/>
- The linkedin page (with a linkedin icon):
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecobulkeu/>

Further below the partner logos are shown, and underneath, the dissemination disclaimer of the project (“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 730456”) next to a small EU flag.

3.3 Illustrations

The description of the action was then translated into a set of visuals, with slides for each scene to show the storyboard.

“ECOBULK is a large-scale demonstration of a design driven circular approach and business model for composite materials and products, with solutions targeting every stage in the lifecycle.”

“ECOBULK is creating a new Circular Design Framework, to help designers and manufacturers consider how products can be used, repaired and refurbished to maintain higher value for longer. Material and energy recovery through recycling is a last resort.”

“Demonstrations include the automotive, construction and furniture sectors – but the results are applicable to any industry.”

“The new motorsport park Kymiring, under construction in Finland, will use ECOBULK solutions for lightweight constructions using new materials from recycled multilayer plastic pipes and composite turbine blades.”

“In Italy, new furniture designs will feature innovative binding methods that avoid toxic substances and use recycled materials that can be reused many times.”

“New modular console parts for cars, made from circular bioplastics – thus avoiding the use of fossil fuels - will show how parts can be easily replaced and refurbished.”

“Follow our progress on our website and social media.”

4 VIDEO 2 DESCRIPTION

This chapter will give an overview of the second video from a functional and design perspective.

4.1 Overview

Main Message:

The message is overview of the results of the re-designed composite products using the design framework in the automotive, construction and furniture sectors.

There should also be a some note about the supporting technologies and platforms that make circularity possible in the background.

Target Audiences:

- Circular Economy Stakeholders – the project results are mostly relevant to people who might want to engage in circular product design and manufacture, thus making it a more technical audience than usual.
- Public – while not directly targeting the public in general, the video should communicate the essence of the results so that we can inspire and move social attitudes towards a greater acceptance of circularity and the consumer behaviours that are necessary for it to be possible.

Message Level: Technical

The project and complexity of the prototypes are too great to be able to present the message at a level for all audiences, within a reasonable video length. We have to assume some general knowledge of circular economy and at least a recognition of composite materials as a type of plastic materials. In fact, the new video should be a good complement to the first and should assume the same tone and level.

The project goal in the end is to prove that circularity is possible for composite materials and products. This is much more a message for industry and perhaps policy makers rather than consumers.

4.2 Narrative Structure

Demonstration Project

The project is demonstrating it is possible to create new more circular parts and products to replace existing linear ones in the automotive, furniture and construction sectors.

Design Framework

To guide the design stage into making more circular compatible choices, the partners have developed a Circular Design Framework. This framework helps product designers to consider the relevant options available to promote circularity through circular strategies and design aspects.

Automotive Demonstrators

In the automotive sector we have had 3 demonstrations of central dashboard components being redesigned to be more circular. This is because dashboard parts are not usually salvaged at the end of life. They are difficult to remove and end up as part of the automotive shredder residue, where it is difficult to separate plastics.

One demonstration used a 2k injection moulding technique to include recycled plastics behind a virgin layer. Another used a modular design to help extend the life of the car by being able to replace it and developed a new long-life lease business model for the car. The last tried to find a bio-based plastic as a drop-in replacement for its current production line.

Furniture Demonstrator

The furniture demonstrator focused on a modular concept that allows furniture to be reconfigured as needs change and damaged parts to be easily exchanged. This should greatly increase the longevity of the furniture and its components.

The components themselves are made of a new particle board material that has been adapted to be able to incorporate a much higher percentage of recycled particle board content during production.

The business model for this furniture is also planned to be an institutional lease model where the producer can maintain the furniture.

Construction Demonstrator

The construction demonstrations are based on the GFRP waste-based materials and construction products developed during the project. GFRP waste is increasing over a number of industries, most notably the wind power industry which uses GFRPs in the wind turbine blades.

Since there are currently few to no options for EoL turbine blades, it is important to create new paths to divert them from landfill or incineration.

By putting the GFRP containing waste as a filler inside other recycled (or virgin) plastics, they can be given structural properties that allow them to be used for light construction applications such as sheds and shelters. These are

weatherproof so great for outdoor use, and when they are finished they can fully and easily recycled.

Enabling Technologies

Circularity and the prototypes depend on a number of solutions that make the new lifecycles possible. This includes a number of processes for collection and sorting wastes, as well as cleaning them before recycling.

There is also a large complexity issue in the challenge to gather, track and exchange the required information to scale up the circular economy. At the end of life, products and materials are in an unknown condition and making decisions about what the best options are can be difficult. This is why Ecobulk has also developed a stakeholder platform that can help gather and exchange the necessary information. To make it easier, and more optimal, a decision support system has been created to help decide what to do with products when they are done.

Finally, to be able to give good advice, the DSS must also have information on the condition and history of the product or material. This can be tracked using a QR code that users and stakeholders can scan to get and supply information on the product.

Call to Action

Get in contact with or follow the project to learn more about framework and the wider circular model being developed by Ecobulk.

5 VIDEO 2 DESIGN

5.1 Ecobulk Final Video -Script Proposal

Introduction

ECOBULK is a large-scale European initiative which demonstrates that re-using, upgrading, refurbishing, and recycling composite products is possible, profitable, sustainable and appealing.

To demonstrate our new circular model, in which products are designed to never to become waste, we have selected bulky composite products in the furniture, automotive and building sectors.

Ecobulk focusses on Changes in product designs and New material developments

In the automotive sector new materials supporting sustainability and circularity of plastic composites will be having the main role in designing and manufacturing easy to replace and refurbish internal car parts.

Design

Ecobulk believes circularity begins with design. Using the developed design guidelines, manufacturers can integrate the requirements for circularity in the later steps of the product lifecycle.

Table 2 Circular design strategies for composite products, additions for composite materials in bold

Design aim	Preserving product integrity			Preserving material integrity	
circular economy Strategies	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Actions / Processes	Physical-durability Long use Reuse	Repair Maintenance Adapt Upgrade	Refurbishment Remanufacture Parts - harvesting	Repurpose Resize Reshape	Remould Mechanical Thermal Chemical

Automotive Sector

Composite components such as the central consoles have a long life and do not typically need replacing. They are small, difficult to extract, and currently there is no market for the recovered composites, making it uneconomic to remove them. They are also difficult to recycle since they can mix several different polymer families.

Central console components were redesigned by partners Maier, CRF and MicroCab.

Using 2k injection molding CRF and Maier have maintained the aesthetic qualities with virgin material on the front and use recycled material in the back with a dual layer production process. Using compatible materials ensures these can be recycled at end of life.

Business Model

Furniture Sector

A modular concept allows a variety of products to be created combining simple components.

The modules are all connected with durable metal fasteners that use screws rather than glue to simplify assembly and dis-assembly for maintenance and interchange of damaged parts.

Figure 4 Connection selection to enable dis- & reassembly, reconfiguration and interchangeability of parts.

The particle board uses a new eco-friendly binder material that enables increase recycled content up to 50%.

Upholstery on the units are made of 100% recyclable materials and use Velcro to attach, for extra ease of exchange and maintenance.

Business Model

Initial calculations show a rental model for institutional furniture which allows the manufacturer to maintain the furniture yields positive results after 3.5 years.

Building Sector

In the light construction sector partner Conenor used glass fibre reinforced thermoset plastic (GFRP) waste taken from End of Life wind turbine blades as well as other GFRP-manufacturing waste as reinforcement to produce extruded composite profiles and panels for structural applications like shelters, cabins and benches. These materials are weather resistant, and 100% re-manufacturable with as little as 25% virgin material while keeping similar material properties.

Lipor (Portugal)

Warwick (UK)

FCBA (France)

Business Model

By 2025 it is expected 683,000 tonnes of composite waste will be generated annually. This new material and process can provide a volume and fully circular business model, at a price point comparable to other competing materials and potentially offering a positive net value disposal route.

Enabling Technologies

Making circular decisions about waste can be tricky. Intelligent suggestions based on data gathered through an end-user and stakeholder platform will help. The platform also functions as a marketplace.

A QR code is used to track a material's history and inform users on their options.

Outro

Contact us or visit our website to find out more.

5.2 Script and Action on Screen

ECOBULK is demonstrating that re-using, refurbishing, and recycling composite products is possible, profitable, and sustainable.

The video starts with the presentation of the logo animated into shape.

Composite products were re-designed in the furniture, automotive and building sectors; supported by new materials, processes and platforms enabling a circular lifecycle.

We cut into highlighting the three sectors that were re-designed, supported by captions and animated icons of "Furniture", "Automotive", and "Building", transitioning into another set of captions highlighting the Material, Processes and Platforms, closing into an animation representing the circular lifecycle.

The Ecobulk design guidelines help manufacturers integrate circularity features into products.

We cut into seeing the book of Ecobulk guidelines, first the cover, and then turning a couple of pages.

Central console parts in cars are difficult to extract and recycle, and recovered materials do not meet aesthetic requirements.

We see a car console, zooming in into the central part of the console.

With 2k injection moulding, aesthetic and structural qualities are met using virgin on top of recycled material. Compatible polymer families ensure recyclability at end-of-life, where a zig-zag separator obtains high purity textile fibres and plastics from automotive shredder residue.

We see a simplified 2k injection mould, producing a console part, then we cut into seeing a zig-zag separator working.

The Vianova hydrogen vehicle uses a modular 'switch pack' within a lease model extending lifespan and preserving value for 20 years through timely maintenance and refurbishment.

We see an image of the Vianova, and then transition into a circular graphic of the different parts highlighting the circular lifecycle.

This modular concept creates a variety of products by combining simple components.

We see modular furniture coming together from simple components.

Small damages can lead to entire furniture being thrown away. Parts connected with invisible metal fasteners avoid glue, simplifying replacements.

We zoom in into the connection of the parts of the furniture, showing the metal fasteners.

The particle board uses a new eco-friendly binder material that enables up to 50% recycled content, maintaining properties and low emissions.

We show a pile of boards, zooming in into one of them showing the inside of the board.

Upholstery is made of recyclable materials and slips on or is attached with a pin.

And we see an upholstery piece attaching itself to the furniture.

A rental model for institutional furniture where the manufacturer maintains the furniture can yield profits after 3.5 years.

We cut into a graphic of the "Revenue and Cost", of the furniture leasing model, going up.

Extruded composite profiles and panels produced with GFRPs from wind turbine blades, combined with limited virgin material, are suitable for light outdoor structures. The materials are weather resistant, and re-manufacturable through at least 3 lifecycles.

We see a wind turbine structure, it starts to get dismantled by the removal of the panels. The panels are then destroyed into smaller (dirt-sized) pieces and then these pieces are made into new (refurbished) panels that pile up. Meanwhile, captions highlight its "Weather Resistant" and "Re-Manufacturable" qualities.

This new patented process provides a high volume, fully circular business model, with prices comparable to competing materials and potentially offers a positive net value disposal route.

We cut into an animated graphic, showing “Price point comparisons for Ecobulk products”.

Making good decisions about waste can be tricky. A support system makes suggestions based on data gathered through an end-user and stakeholder platform.

We see a couple of trash bins, one labeled “Repair”, one labeled “Reuse”, and an arm holding a piece of plastic. Finally the Reuse bin glows and the hand throws the plastic into the bin.

A QR code is used to track a material’s history and inform users on their options.

We transition into the QR code and a smartphone scanning it, showing the material information on the screen.

Find out more at ecobulk.eu

And we see with the Ecobulk logo, along the “ecobulk.eu” website, cutting into a splash page of the partners, the dissemination disclaimer (“This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456.”), and the EU flag.

5.3 Illustrations

With 2k injection moulding, aesthetic and structural qualities

are met using virgin on top of recycled material.

Compatible polymer families ensure recyclability at end-of-life, where a zig-zag separator

obtains high purity textile fibres and plastics from automotive shredder residue.

The Vianova hydrogen vehicle uses a modular 'switch pack'

within a lease model extending lifespan and preserving value for 20 years through timely maintenance and refurbishment.

This modular concept creates a variety of products by combining simple components.

Small damages can lead to entire furniture being thrown away.

Parts connected with invisible metal fasteners avoid glue, simplifying replacements.

The particle board uses a new eco-friendly binder material that enables

Upholstery is made of recyclable materials and slips on or is attached with a pin.

A rental model for institutional furniture where the manufacturer maintains the furniture can yield profits after 3.5 years.

Extruded composite profiles and panels produced with GFRPs from wind turbine blades,

combined with limited virgin material, are suitable for light outdoor structures.

The materials are weather resistant, and re-manufacturable through at least 3 lifecycles.

This new patented process provides a high volume, fully circular business model, with prices comparable to competing materials and potentially offers a positive net value disposal route.

